

Tejiendo Datos

*Interwoven Urban
Trajectories: Gender,
Technology, and Care*

Mónica Humeres, Angela Cura, Felipe Palma y
Eduardo Graells-Garrido

Corresponding author:
Mónica Humeres
Assistant Professor
Department of Social Communication
Faculty of Communication and Image
Universidad de Chile
monica.humeres@uchile.cl

Short Introduction to the Empirical Data

My empirical material consists of ten ethnographic mobility shadowing journeys with women caregivers in Santiago and Valparaíso, Chile. The dataset is documented through **three** complementary recording modes: (1) **audio recordings of in-depth interviews** conducted while moving through the city; (2) **video recordings** (approximately 34 hours of footage); and (3) a **textile cartography of the journeys** in the form of Khipu-inspired artworks that represent the extension of trajectories, the number of stops, and the combination of transport modes.

Across this material, a key puzzle remains: even these representations may fail to convey the full density of lived experience. This tension, between what can be traced, modelled, or visualised, and what remains irreducible, makes the dataset particularly suitable for collective interpretation as raw data.

Introduction

Today, much of public transport planning is based on data generated through our digital interactions with technologies such as mobile applications, GPS, and electronic fare cards. These records are processed through algorithms that aim to model our movements in order to make routes more “efficient”.

But efficient for whom? In filling informational gaps, these algorithms infer trajectories from predefined patterns. They often project an individual who travels alone—without interruptions or burdens—from home to work and back; someone who does not provision a household, does not organise care, and does not fear sexual violence.

That figure corresponds to an experience historically more associated with men, as a consequence of the sexual division of labour. By assuming it as the norm, these systems reinforce a logic of efficiency centred on formal work and linear trajectories, excluding other forms of mobility that are equally everyday.

What falls outside this framework, and therefore outside the record, are the fragmented, multiple, and chained journeys undertaken by many people, especially women, on a daily basis. These are trajectories shaped by care work: accompanying children and older adults, running errands, and combining flexible employment with domestic labour. Such movements are not exceptional. They are structural to the reproduction of life and to social functioning, yet they are rarely considered by the systems that organise mobility.

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This installation is grounded in a research project that seeks to make visible those underrepresented trajectories. It combines quantitative data with a qualitative perspective, drawing on ethnographic follow-alongs (N=10) conducted in the Metropolitan Region and Valparaíso. Based on this material, we produced textile pieces that represent real journeys, including their temporalities, obstacles, situated decisions, and strategies of adaptation.

*“Es una aventura diaria con mi hijo. Pero, a pesar
Igual, me gusta poder
recorreremos. Quizás algún
grande, pueda recordar
‘Mira, por aquí pasé’
que las políticas de trans
más las necesidades de las
comodidad son clave para*

*[la movilidad], sobre todo
de todo, lo disfruto [...] mostrarle los lugares que
día cuando sea más
estos trayectos y decir:
[...]. Solo que sería bueno
porte público consideraran
cuidadoras. El tiempo y la
nosotras”.*

(Andrea, 33 años, Santiago, madre de un niño de 4).

Each piece raises an underlying question: What realities are left out when digital systems interpret our everyday movements? How is a “typical trip” defined within algorithmic models, and why does it reflect a masculine ideal? What role do information technologies play in public decisions about mobility and in everyday lived experiences? What other languages and materials allow us to represent experiences that digital data fail to capture?

This installation invites us to rethink the digitalisation of data as an instrument of knowledge, from a perspective that recognises data as a form of power: they shape what becomes visible, what is managed, and who matters in the co-production of public space.

Urban mobilities

gender-differentiated in Santiago

Comparison based on the Household Origin–Destination Survey (EHO-D)

These two maps separate the journeys made by women (left) and men (right) in Santiago. In each map, trips are distinguished by purpose:

in orange, care-related travel;
in green, travel related to work or study.

The information comes from more than 100,000 respondents to the 2012 Household Origin-Destination Survey (EHO-D), the last survey of its kind conducted in Santiago, and one that has since been discontinued.

The contrast between both maps reveals clear differences in patterns and motives of mobility. In the women's map, care-related trajectories (orange) predominate: they are shorter, multiple, and fragmented. In the men's map, trips related to work or study (green) stand out, generally longer and more linear. This difference reflects how care responsibilities—which disproportionately fall on women—directly shape how they move through the city.

Note: The available data are organised under binary gender categories. This project questions this classification and acknowledges that other gender identities are also rendered invisible by current technical systems.

Trajectory Khipus:

chained trips that algorithms fail to reconstruct

Craft Technique for Data Physicalization

The installation uses an *embarrilado* technique over sheep wool fleece. The fleece provides a neutral, volumetric base, while colored threads wrapped around it encode data variables. In the khipu-inspired cartographies developed for this project, thread color represents transport modes and travel duration. Bulky fleece nodes, formed by concentrated wrapping, indicate stops within the journey.

This *embarrilado-over-fleece* approach is intentionally modular and transferable. Data variables can be mapped onto combinations of thread color, wrapping density, node size, and spatial arrangement, enabling the representation of sequential or relational datasets. Beyond visual legibility, the material properties of wool and thread produce a tactile, sensorially diverse surface, supporting embodied exploration and opening possibilities for inclusive data interpretation within craft-based data physicalization

Comparison between women's real care-related journeys and their digital version.

Khampus de trayectorias:

chained trips that algorithms fail to reconstruct.

This piece represents ten everyday mobility journeys carried out by women caregivers in Santiago and Valparaíso. Using a method known as ethnographic shadowing (Jirón, 2010), we accompanied their routes in order to document—in real time—walking, waiting, interruptions, and care-related activities.

Inspired by khipus, ancestral Andean record-keeping systems made of cords and knots, we created two hanging lines for each case:

one line shows the real journey, as each woman actually carried it out;

the other shows the journey projected by the ADATRAP software algorithm, which infers trajectories based on Bip! card data and bus GPS.

This algorithm applies a set of predefined rules (around eight) to fill in missing information, such as drop-off points or the presumed continuity of a journey.

Comparison between women's real care-related journeys and their digital version.

Whipus de trayectorias:

chained trips that algorithms fail to reconstruct.

In this installation, we applied the same rules used by the ADATRAP **algorithm** to the ethnographic journeys in order to estimate how they would be digitally interpreted. As a result, in nine of the ten cases analysed, the real journeys—chained through multiple purposes—were interpreted as a set of independent trips, without recognising them as part of a single sequence.

The piece demonstrates how algorithmic models render trip chaining, a mobility pattern characteristic of care work, invisible.

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